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Structure and function of the reflex arc

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The structural basis of the reflex is the reflex arc, which includes several mandatory components, or links, each of which performs its own function. In this section, we will study the functions of the links of the reflex arc. Knowledge of the structure of specific reflex arcs, with the help of which the regulation of the function of a particular system (regulation of blood pressure, respiration, processes of digestion or excretion) is absolutely necessary for the practice of a doctor. The fact is that the pathology of any organ or a violation of the activity of an organ system can be associated with a violation of the function of any link of the corresponding reflex arc.

Reflex Arc is a set of formations necessary for the implementation of a reflex. Any reflex arc consists of five obligatory joints. receptor -1, afferent link -2, central link -3, efferent link -4 and effector -5. the central link of the somatic reflex arc is the anterior branches of the gray matter of the spinal cord. The centers of reflex arcs can be any part of the central nervous system.

Receptors perceive a certain type of irritation (heat, cold, pressure, light, vibrations, stretching, etc.) and transform into a nerve impulse, which is transmitted to the central nervous system. The task of receptors is to translate

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various stimuli into the language of the nervous system: nerve impulses transmitted at different frequencies.

The accumulation of receptors, the irritation of which causes strictly defined reflexes, is called reception fields or reflexogenic zones.

According to the location of the receptors, it is possible to distinguish extero-, interoceptive and proprioceptive, reflexes - reflexes that occur when specific receptors are stimulated. For example, pulling back a hand in case of a burn is an exteroceptive reflex, a knee-jerk reflex, which we observe in a neurologist's office in response to a hammer blow, is proprioceptive.

The afferent link of the reflex arc is represented by neurons whose processes connect receptors with nerve centers, provide centripetal conduction of excitation to the structures of the central nervous system. Most afferent nerve fibers that carry information from tactile, temperature, pain and mechanoreceptors belong to group A and conduct excitation from receptive fields in nerve centers at a speed of 80 - 120 m / s.

NERVE CENTERS - a set of nerve cells, an "ensemble" of neurons that are involved in the regulation of a specific function or in the implementation of a specific reflex act.

We will analyze the properties of the nerve centers in detail later, but for now we will note only the functional significance of the centers. In the nerve center, the integration of all information coming through the afferent pathways takes place, and a command for action comes from the center.

Depending on the location of the nerve centers, there are **SPINAL** reflexes - the nerve centers are located in the segments of the spinal cord, **BULBAR** - in the

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medulla oblongata, MESENCEPHAL - in the structures of the midbrain, cortical - in various areas of the cerebral cortex. For example, pulling a hand when burned is a spinal reflex.

In accordance with the function performed among the nerve centers, sensitive centers, centers of autonomic functions, and motor centers can be distinguished. In addition, it is possible to distinguish structurally organized centers that regulate a specific function: the vasomotor center, the respiratory center, the center of salivation.

